

GNU/Linux and its place through history

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Abstract

In today's world we are witnesses to ever more increasing usage of systems based on GNU/Linux. Be it in datacenters as hypervisors, stand alone servers, foundations for cloud based computing, or as an embedded solution like smart phones, entertainment platforms, medical devices, micro controllers etc, it is obvious that this platform has made its impact and not without a good reason. We shall explore how it all came to be, how can it be used and under which terms, what are the implications and what could be the possible future.

Keywords: open source; GNU Linux; embedded; server.